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THE FORMATION OF UKRAINIAN ECONOMIC MENTALITY PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES IN THE COMMAND-ADMINISTRATIVE ECONOMY

ОСОБЛИВОСТІ ФОРМУВАННЯ ПСИХОЛОГІЧНИХ РИС УКРАЇНСЬКОГО ГОСПОДАРСЬКОГО МЕНТАЛІТЕТУ В УМОВАХ КОМАНДНО- АДМІНІСТРАТИВНОЇ ЕКОНОМІКИ

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The economic mentality is the basis of the institutional structure of the national economy, which projects the information laid down by historical experience in all spheres of social life, including its economic component, determines the essence of the institutional system, the stability of its institutional structure. Norms and stereotypes of economic behavior, formed on the basis of strong features of the economic mentality, lead to efficient allocation of resources, economic growth. However, the main features of the economic mentality of Ukrainians contradict the formal institutions of an efficient market economy, as most of them were formed under the influence of Soviet economic culture, with its anti-liberal understanding of economic freedom and legal consciousness. decisions, obedience to the law, honesty and transparency in establishing economic relations with other agents, active economic activity, which is focused on achieving strategic goals. That is why the analysis of the era of political and economic dependence of Ukraine opens up opportunities to identify the main features of economic mentality that hinders the implementation of basic strategies of economic behavior at the present stage.

Analysis of recent research and publications

The problem of economic mentality, its close connection with the level of socio-economic development of society, historical preconditions of its formation in Russian and Ukrainian science began to be actively developed only in the mid-90s in the works of Popov V., Komikh N., Gaidai T., Gritsenko A., Vukolova T., Efremenko T., Filipchenko A., Oleynik A. and others.

At the present stage of socio-economic development, it may be important for different countries to find the optimal strategy, which would take into account the peculiarities and contradictions of the national economic mentality. Different authors (Bendix, J. (2018), Kubiniy H. (2019), Pishchik V.,

Лусте О.О. Особливості формування психологічних рис українського господарського менталітету в умовах командно-адміністративної економіки. Науково-методична стаття.

У статті проаналізовано командно-адміністративну систему господарювання та основні складові радянської економічної культури; досліджено вплив системи державного патерналізму на рівень економічної свободи господарюючих суб'єктів та трансформацію господарського менталітету українців; визначено основні фактори формування економічного менталітету в радянський період; виділено риси економічної залежності в структурі господарського менталітету.

Ключові слова: господарський менталітет, економічна культура, стратегія розвитку, корпоративна культура, економічна поведінка

Luste O.O. Features of Ukrainian economic mentality psychological features in the conditions of command-administrative economy. Scientific and methodical article.

The article analyzes the command-administrative system of management and the main components of the Soviet economic culture; the influence of the system of state paternalism on the level of economic freedom of business entities and the transformation of the economic mentality of Ukrainians has been investigated; the main factors of the formation of the economic mentality in the Soviet period are determined; the features of economic dependence in the structure of the economic mentality are highlighted.

Keywords: economic mentality, economic culture, development strategy, corporate culture, economic behavior

Belousova A. (2020). Biermann P., Welsch H. (2021), come to similar conclusions, that this strategy cannot be implemented in the short term due to radical reforms, this requires a much longer historical period of change not only in politics and economics, but also in the structure of the economic mentality.

Therefore, solving the problem of economy modernization should undoubtedly take into account the process of reforming some features of the national economic mentality, which involves not denying historically formed values and models of economic behavior, but the use of progressive mental features and gradual abandonment of economically inefficient.

Gaidai (2006) distinguishes the following levels in the structure of economic mentality:

- the level of the unconscious (subconscious, collective unconscious);
- level of consciousness (awareness, reflection);
- the level of individual mentality (unity of conscious and subconscious values);
- the level of non-individual mentality (the mentality of the social group, society, the unity of the commonly accepted within their limits of mental traits and settings) [7].

Vukolova (2004) offers in the structure of economic mentality to allocate the following components:

- structural: value-motivational attitude to labor and wealth, various sources of income, property; norms and models of socio-economic interaction in the process of production, distribution, exchange and consumption; institutionalized and non-institutionalized forms of objectification of economic mentality;
- image: organizational forms of economic activity (creation of individual, private, collective, state enterprises, etc.); stereotypes of consumption (orientation to the average opinion, high degree of orientation to non-market methods of providing consumer services, psychology of subsistence level, etc.); freedom, morality, work as a self-worth of life, welfare, initiative, tradition, independence, legality [22].

Unsolved aspects of the problem

Common to most studies is the recognition that economic reforms in Ukraine in the 1990s did not take into account the level of unpreparedness of both the economic system and society as a whole, mainly due to the conflict between the market nature of these reforms and non-market economic mentality. But in the mentioned works there are no comprehensive studies of the problem of economic mentality of Ukrainian economic entities, the main historical determinants of the national economic mentality are still unclear.

The purpose of this article is to study the historical process of formation of the peculiarities of the Ukrainian economic mentality in the era of command-administrative economy.

The main part

The current dynamics of the market environment

development is characterized by the intensification of globalization and integration processes, due to which the differences in the character and mechanism of the functioning of various national models of economic growth, influenced by the historical progress of society, become apparent.

In our opinion, this problem actualizes the role of the mentality of society, its influence on the process of economic activity, since it is the very mentality that accumulates in itself the historical memory of the people, reflecting through the economic activity of its representatives the most important values, norms and arrangements adopted for this society. Unlike the ideological guides and rapidly changing public attitudes, mentality is a long-term factor in human economic behavior, a factor in social development or decline, depending on which mental characteristics are dominant for a particular nation.

The economic mentality is a long-term determinant of economic behavior, a factor of social progress or regress, depending on which characteristics are dominant in the mental structure of the nation. It manifests the influence on socio-economic transformations at the micro-, meso- and macro levels, representing the main motives and models of employee behavior, and determines their level of economic activity. Economic mentality allows forming different approaches to management styles, functioning and development of the organizational structure of the enterprise. Under the influence of economic mentality, the processes of socialization of the country's economy are taking place, it promotes economic integration of the country, the formation of its competitive potential, determines the level of its economic freedom.

Considering the possibility of using the national economic mentality to ensure the effectiveness of socio-economic reforms, it should be emphasized that the subjects of the economic mentality are not only individual consumers, entrepreneurs, but also government officials. This means that measures aimed at forming models of economic behavior adequate to modern market requirements should also be carried out at the macro level.

The analysis of economic mentality structure and the identification of the correlation between its individual components and indicators of socio-economic development of states shows that priority in the implementation of modernization reforms should be given to support those features of economic mentality that contribute to positive economic dynamics.

It is possible to offer the measures helping to use features of economic mentality at various levels of economic system functioning:

- Megalevel: the formation of a positive image of the country is taking into account strong mental traits: collectivism and statehood (in structuring the negotiation process), patience (in foreign trade operations and production activities with foreign capital).
- Macro level: creation of national centers of national mentality research with branches in the

regions and enterprises, the purpose of which is to identify the ratio of strong and weak mental traits of the population in the country, as well as modeling specific management systems at all levels.

- Mesolevel: development by regional and socio-psychological services special questionnaires that will study attitudes to work, wealth, propensity to save, desire for economic independence, propensity for economic paternalism, interest in conducting and implementing socio-economic reforms, trust in political institutions, the degree of perception of foreign experience, etc. in representatives of individual regions. It is planned to create centers whose task is to promote investment in innovation. In this case, the desire for something new is the mental basis of transformations, which primarily change the worldview of entrepreneurs and managers.
- Microlevel: the formation of corporate culture of the organization with a combination of elements of the capitalist mentality (rationality – the desire

for wealth, the desire to earn and the desire to invest; honesty – willingness to fulfill commitments; independence; desire for leadership; desire for innovation; willingness to take risks) and promising features of the economic mentality.

Considering the role of the Soviet totalitarian state in the formation of the Ukrainian economic mentality, it should be noted that its institutional system reflects the features of the classical model of the eastern state (Fig. 1) [8, p.42]. In this model, the state is the primary, unifying link of economic entities. Collective psychology requires an organizational center, which is the state. Ukrainian society is characterized by a primary search for an idea, spirit, common goal and inner self-knowledge. On the other hand, the inability of the individual from within to change the system of society has led him to take a position of anticipation, lack of initiative, passivity of economic entities within the socialist economy. Changes in the economy spread only from above, while covering the entire system.

Figure1. Institutional model of the Soviet state

Source: compiled by authors on materials [13].

The main prerequisite for the formation of command-administrative methods of management was the insecurity of one of the most important institutions of a market economy – the institution of private property. If for economically developed countries, private property was a condition of individual independence, then in a distributive economy, it determined his subordination to state interests. A long-standing tradition inherited from the Soviet economy has been the very weak protection of economic actors, which has contributed to the development of public property institutions. One of the features of public property is the lack of an individual or social group of the full rights to a tangible or intangible object. Historically, the struggle for economic resources was not so much in their appropriation,

Inadequate protection of property rights was determined by the low level of economic confidence in society, unfavorable investment climate, outflow of resources, repatriation of profits, chronic lack of state resources to implement their own programs. There was a vicious circle when instability led to a lack of

resources, and the need to attract additional resources was to ensure the right of the state at the right time to "press" the owner, changing the rules of the economic game at its discretion.

In the 20th century, the Ukrainian mentality became the object of social utopia, in particular Soviet-communist. Stereotypes in relation to labor (the cult of abstract labor) of consumption (asceticism), distribution (egalitarianism), social relations (collectivism) have become the property of the Ukrainian mentality [16]. The political regime in the USSR was based on non-economic traditions coercion by the authoritarian state and the "dependent" features of national culture – the willingness of the population to delegate their rights, the primacy of the public over the personal, the suppression of individual rights and freedoms. Scholars define the country's transformations as "conservative modernization", as the transformation of an agrarian country into an industrial and military superpower, providing social guarantees were carried out on the basis of archaic institutions – repressive-administrative forms of government, total state

control over citizens, elimination of civil and civil institutions. rule of law, demonetization, social practices of collectivism and equal distribution, restriction of freedom of individual choice. The fact that the communist system was established and lasted for seven decades testifies to the acceptability of conditions for the majority of the population, economic guarantees in exchange for individual freedom. In the USSR socially-economic dependence of citizens on the state was total, as it was based on the state monopoly on all economic resources of society.

The most important element of any free society is an independent person with its own resources, which plays an indispensable role in maintaining free thought and the general atmosphere of independence from state control [11]. To ensure total control over society, the Soviet state had to destroy, above all, such an independent person and ensure a monopoly on economic resources. Institutional activities structures of totalitarian society was aimed at controlling and subordinating the resources of various social groups, as it is "the monopoly on resources – a key strategy of all forms of power play" [7]. The paternalism of the state in relation to its citizens stems from the concentration in its hands of the resources necessary for the livelihood and social protection of the population, which provide the state with the opportunity to act as a subject of coercion.

In the Soviet economy, such a concentration of resources was achieved by nationalizing industry, depriving citizens of private ownership of the means of production and housing, banning all forms of private enterprise, and sharply reducing trade and money circulation. In the first decade of Soviet rule, "foreign elements", the "exploiting class", ie the owners, amateur, entrepreneurial segments of the population were exterminated. The experience of totalitarianism confirms that if freedom requires guarantees of property rights, then the desire for unlimited personal power over citizens requires depriving citizens of economic power over resources, as it allows them to break free from the grip of comprehensive state power [2].

The state provided itself with the opportunity to accumulate the basic part of the national income, and life benefits in excess of the established minimum were provided to citizens in the form of "allotment". Agents The implementation of the policy of state paternalism in the USSR was advocated by local authorities, enterprises, and trade unions, which were burdened with social obligations. Under paternalism, workers received real and substantial non-wage benefits. The employee came to the company not so much to earn as to receive resources from public consumption funds (housing, scarce goods, medical and spa services for himself and his family members, places in children's preschools, etc.). All these benefits a citizen could not get outside the company for a number of reasons:

- inability to pay for these benefits due to low incomes;
- lack of market for these goods and services.

As a result, the Soviet man remained, firstly, economically dependent on the structures of the distributive state and his enterprise, and secondly, completely replaceable in terms of national tasks. The concentration of all decisions in the hands of power in itself creates a state of affairs when the structure that still remains in society is imposed on him by the state, and individuals become interchangeable units that have no other definite and established relationship with each other than established by this organization [10]

The Soviet state deprived citizens of independent livelihood resources, and the total economic dependence of the people, in turn became the basis for non-economic coercion, subordination of man to state interests. Providing citizens financially, the state ensured full control over their actions. Such charitable despotism recognizes the patron party's right to apply sanctions or incentives to regulate the behavior of the dependent party in various spheres of life. The command-and-control economy was based on a combination of coercion ("commands") and moral and ethical stimulus reactions.

The paternalistic system of government narrowed the space for exchange, and all social ties in Soviet society were "vertical" hierarchical. This meant that one party (the state) concentrated resources in their hands, through "bargaining" and "coercion" dictated to the other party (society) the conditions of exchange. People were obliged to conform to the way of life imposed on them by the authorities. The man had no right not to work. The condition for obtaining social benefits from the state was compulsory employment in social production. Throughout its history, the Soviet economy has been in short supply: the emphasis on the development of heavy industry, based not on economic calculation but on political and military considerations, required more manpower than society could offer. Therefore, it was necessary to deprive people of freedom of choice of lifestyle and occupation, to subordinate their resources to the needs of the state [11].

The most important social benefits were not earned, but deserved, their amount depended not on the efficiency of human labor, but on many other, non-economic, factors: continuous work experience, participation in social activities. At the same time, the illusion of a "safe" existence was formed in the population. The reasons for this were strict restrictions on the level of consumption, the mobilization of all the country's resources for military needs. Deficit of goods and services, poorly differentiated level of earnings led to the non-monetary nature of the Soviet economy, the limited importance of money as a factor of material well-being.

Thus, the relationship of state paternalism is a typical example of manipulating the behavior of dependent citizens through «bargaining "and" coercion ". The first consequence of the Soviet system of management was the consolidation in the structure of the Ukrainian economic mentality of such cognitive traits as feelings of helplessness, lack of

control and fatalism. The motivational features of the Ukrainian homo economicus was the desire to delegate responsibility for their own well-being. There was a habituation to guaranteed material goods, insurance against poverty regardless of human economic activity. System privileges and privileges formed a set of expectations, which in the late 1980s began to be called "dependent". Socio-economic dependence has become a normative value.

An economically dependent citizen had to constantly remember to whom he owed his well-being. Enterprises and the state in his person received cheap and loyal labor. The mechanism of social security was hidden from the citizens – the accumulation of all economic resources in the hands of the state, depriving people of economic and consumer freedom. Low incomes of citizens led to high significance social guarantees and free social benefits provided state. People were deprived of the opportunity to earn many vital benefits, but guaranteed employment, free education and health care, system of administrative regulation prices strengthened their faith in the fact that they care. Finally, the Soviet economic system reproduced dependent behaviors characteristics of the modal personality of the Ukrainian – the priority of "We" over "I", conformism, dissolution of the interests of a particular economic entity in public [5].

In general, the three main components of Soviet economic culture were:

- moral dimensions of economic activity;
- anti-liberal understanding of economic freedom;
- non-legal consciousness.

Non-economic stimulation of labor in the Soviet economy appealed to community-collectivist values of "being like everyone else" and communist ideology immorality of material interests. Socialist labor morality demanded from the worker high material costs at low material remuneration. The cult of selflessness of Orthodoxy with its ideas about the injustice of wealth, moral inadmissibility economic differentiation and exploitation was consistent with the communist principle of modest prosperity, as the support in the mass consciousness of these values was necessary due to the underdeveloped consumer market, chronic shortages of goods and services.

Thus, in a system based on non-economic incentives, lose their original meaning such values as professionalism, business competence, high employment, and the work is ritual in nature. Absolutization moral dimensions of labor led to the dogmatism of labor consciousness of workers, envy of the more successful and enterprising, unwillingness to succeed on their own but to block others roads moving up.

If the centuries-old restriction of economic freedom in the pre-Soviet period led to the tradition of anarchist understanding of freedom as permissiveness, in the system of Soviet state paternalism it was replaced by socialist understanding of economic freedom as material security. The closed nature of society, the system of severe restrictions on economic activity, along with guaranteed benefits,

stability and predictability of life have developed appropriate adaptive economic strategies and contributed to the formation of a type of person focused on stability and well-being as higher values.

Social protection of citizens by the state was interpreted by the Soviet system as the highest measure of their real economic freedom. Realization of freedom as the presence of external in relation to the individual opportunities to use important benefits depends on opportunities created from the outside, but not from man himself. Material good for all and equal - these are simple and tangible values that stem from simple human needs. On the other hand, economic freedom and independence in making economic decisions are values of a higher order, and therefore more abstract, requiring a certain level of economic, social, cultural, intellectual and ethical development of their bearers.

Of course, in exchange for state support, a certain amount of work was required, but instead they were relieved of the burden of responsibility for themselves. The lack of economic choice also meant the absence of the need for decision-making. People did not need to assess the risks and profitability of their activities, they, without property and capital, were deprived of worries about how to dispose of these resources in exchange for the loss of individuality.

The long development of the national economy within the Soviet command-and-control system complemented the formation of the image of an economically dependent subject of economic relations, which is characterized by the following features of the economic mentality:

- lack of initiative, passivity of economic entities;
- low level of trust in the state in society;
- feelings of helplessness, lack of control and fatalism;
- the desire to delegate responsibility for their own well-being;
- fear of losing state support;
- conformism, dissolution of the interests of a particular economic entity in the public;
- the predominance in labor of "coercion" over "incentive".

Conclusions

Thus, the analysis of the historical development of the command-administrative system of management shows that the most important asset of the Soviet era was the formation of stable negative mental attitudes in the field of economic activity. As a result, we can observe the slowdown in Ukraine's economic development in transition, as the above features do not contribute to the proper motivation of effective economic activity, are in conflict with the socio-economic institutions of developed economies. While Ukrainian society, its economic component is more inclined to the model of the eastern state, the planned reforms have a stable Western vector, so the opportunity to minimize these contradictions at the macro level will appear only if the past experience, maximum openness of Ukrainian society.

Abstract

The current stage of socio-economic development is characterized by structural reforms related to the formation of a competitive market environment, the development of various forms of ownership, the formation of qualitatively new forms of economic organization, deepening integration processes. The author emphasizes that the inconsistency of the interaction of formal and historically formed informal institutions highlights the role of economic mentality, as it directly affects the general vector of development of the socio-economic system. The article draws attention to the informal component of the institutional environment - economic mentality, which characterizes the historically formed values, motives and models of economic behavior of individual and collective actors that directly affect the overall vector of development and transformation of socio-economic system. It is determined that the economic mentality determines the dynamics of development of the institutional environment, influencing the effectiveness of the interaction of formal and informal institutions, ensuring the implementation of complementary functions; mediates the process of institutionalization of historically determined values, stereotypes and models of economic behavior in the system of formal norms and rules; provides under the influence of other socio-economic factors adaptability and dynamism of the institutional structure, promotes the formation and development of new institutions. The purpose of this study is to identify the features of the formation of psychological traits of the Ukrainian economic mentality as a long-term determinant of economic behavior. The methodology is based on the historical analysis of the dependence of the main features of the national economic culture and key elements of the command-administrative economy. As a result, it can be determined that the long-term development of the national economy within the Soviet command-administrative system complemented the formation of the image of economically dependent subject of economic relations, characterized by such features of economic mentality as lack of initiative, passivity of economic entities the desire to delegate responsibility for their own well-being, conformism, the dissolution of the interests of a particular business entity in public, the predominance in the work of "coercion" over "encouragement".

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